

Support stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9

Deliverable 2.6 Carbon Dioxide Removals, article 6 of the Paris agreement

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This is a Horizon Europe project (Coordinated and Support Action) funded by the European Union for 3 years (from 1 July 2022 until 30 June 2025).

Project summary

Support Stakeholders on Carbon Capture Utilisation and Storage of ETIP ZEP and IWG9.

The overarching goal of this project is to bring together and further develop a strong inclusive network of CCUS stakeholders – effectively interconnecting and coordinating the activities of CCUS European Technology Innovation Platforms (ETIP ZEP) and the CCUS SET Plan Implementation Plan Working Group (IWG9) – to support the development and implementation of the SET Plan.

Supporting the alignment and efficient coordination of stakeholders – including industry, researchers, public authorities, civil society – in order to accelerate the delivery of the CCUS research and innovation (R&I) activities and to progress the emerging policy priorities at EU and national level for the implementation of CCUS, will be crucial over the coming years for Europe to reach the ambitious climate targets for 2030 and 2050.

This will be achieved by efficiently aligning and coordinating the activities of ETIP ZEP and the IWG9 in a joint work programme; establishing networks and other fora to enable the stakeholders to collaborate and coordinate effectively, pooling expertise, experience and resources to address common challenges; engaging also with other programmes and external stakeholders; facilitating engagement and creating greater interaction and cohesion between the different CCUS activities; supporting the CCUS community to develop clear strategies and recommendations; accompanied by a strong continuous programme for outreach, dissemination and communication.

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Contact details

+32 2 882 50 07

iwg9@zeroemissionsplatform.eu

www.ccus-setplan.eu

www.zeroemissionsplatform.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement 101075790

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1 INTRODUCTION

Deliverable 2.6: Develop report on Carbon Dioxide Removals, article 6 of the Paris agreement.

ETIP ZEP and IWG9 have identified the delivery of carbon dioxide removals (CDR) as an important component of carbon capture and storage (CCS) and essential for the achievement of carbon neutrality in 2050 and net negative emissions thereafter. This report describes ETIP ZEP and IWG9's interactions with recent policy developments and identifies priorities to support the development of an effective CDR sector and carbon market that instils trust.

1.1 Background

As noted by recent publications from the United Nations Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)¹, around 30-1,090 Gt of engineered carbon removals are needed between 2020 and 2100 alongside emission reductions in order to keep the global average temperature increase within 1.5°C. In the European Union (EU), modelling results show that the achievement of carbon-neutrality by 2050 will require capturing 200-350 MtCO₂ through direct air capture (DACs) and bioenergy with CCS² (BECCS).

These reports show that, while emission reductions must be the priority, the development and deployment of carbon removals is necessary to counterbalance both residual and historical emissions. The volumes of removals needed to enable net-zero require a rapid scale up of these technologies, making it crucial to build up the sector promptly – carbon removals are needed on the transition to net-zero, to enable net-zero, and to achieve net-negative emissions afterwards.

2 THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION'S WORK ON CDR

While there is no EU level target to guide the development of carbon removals, the European Climate Law³ wrote into law the goal to achieve climate neutrality in the EU by 2050, where climate neutrality is defined as the 'balance between anthropogenic economy-wide emissions and removals, through natural and technological solutions, of greenhouse gases domestically within the Union at the latest by 2050'.

¹ IPCC (2022). [Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change](#). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA. doi: 10.1017/9781009157926

² European Commission (2021). [Commission Staff Working Document: Sustainable carbon cycles for a 2050 climate-neutral: EU Technical Assessment Accompanying the Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council Sustainable Carbon Cycles](#).

³ [European Commission, European Climate Law \(2021\)](#).

Following the European Climate Law, the European Commission tabled a Communication on Sustainable Carbon Cycles⁴, setting out a forward-looking plan on how to develop and increase nature- and technology-based carbon removals. Namely, it tabled a proposal on an EU regulatory framework for the certification of carbon removals, which was adopted on 30 November. Supported by a 12-week stakeholder consultation, the proposed framework lays down quality criteria for carbon removal activities, guidelines for verification and certification, as well as the procedure for the recognition of certification schemes. Certification methodologies and more detailed rules will be set out in implementing acts and delegated acts.

The European Commission has engaged an Expert Group of around 70 members involved in the field of carbon removals, including national authorities, industry, NGOs, certification bodies and research institutions, to support with the preparation and implementation of relevant legislative proposals, focusing on the certification methodologies and key issues such as quantification, monitoring and reporting, additionality, durability, environmental integrity and transparency. In 2023, the group will conduct preparatory work, gathering best practices on certification schemes.

The European Commission has also been cooperating with international partners in the field of CDR, notably under the remit of Mission Innovation (MI), a global initiative joining 23 countries and the European Union, aimed at accelerating public and private investment in research, development, and demonstration in clean energy. The work of MI is developed through 7 missions, including Carbon Dioxide Removal. The goal of the CDR mission is to enable CDR technologies to achieve a net reduction of 100 MtCO₂ per year globally by 2030. The CDR Mission is co-led by the United States, Saudi Arabia, and Canada, and focuses on three technical areas – Direct Air Capture with Storage, Biomass with Carbon Removal and Storage, and Enhanced Mineralisation. The European Commission/Directorate General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) is participating in the CDR Mission as a supporting member. Norway is participating as core member of the mission, represented by Gassnova.

3 WORK ON CDR IN ETIP ZEP AND IWG9

Recognising the importance of scaling up carbon removals already in the lead up to 2030, and the outstanding issues that need further work in order to drive an effective deployment, ETIP ZEP, who has previously delivered two reports focusing on a definition for carbon removals (2020)⁵ and on a robust accounting framework (2021)⁶, has engaged a broad group of stakeholders (including from academia, industry and environmental NGOs) to work on this topic.

⁴ European Commission (2021). [Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council: Sustainable Carbon Cycles](#).

⁵ ZEP (2020). [Europe needs a definition of Carbon Dioxide Removal](#).

⁶ ZEP (2021). [Europe needs robust accounting for Carbon Dioxide Removal](#).

ETIP ZEP has, through its Temporary Working Group (TWG) Mission CDR, actively given input to the CDR Mission of Mission Innovation (*see above*), including to the Innovation Roadmap⁷ and Launchpad⁸. Namely, the focus of the TWG CDR has been to:

- Support the European Commission / DG RTD on its work related the CDR Mission.
- Follow and provide input to the CDR Mission, ensuring that its programme and activities are aligned with key messages from ETIP ZEP and IWG9 reports and recommendations.

In order to streamline ETIP ZEP's work related to CDR and given the many policy developments in this area in the EU and internationally, the scope of the TWG CDR was extended to also include the following objectives:

- Follow the European Commission's proposal on certificates for carbon removals and provide input as appropriate.
- Develop further the ETIP ZEP position on CDR.
- Follow and support ETIP ZEP's participation in the expert group on carbon removals.
- Follow the developments on carbon accounting methodologies, voluntary markets and Article 6 of the Paris agreement and the needed regulatory frameworks.

Following the endorsement of the new Terms of Reference, the TWG CDR started to work on a feedback note to the European Commission proposal on the establishment of a Union certification framework for carbon removals and prepared a response to the Article 6.4 Supervisory Body call for input on carbon removals. In addition, ETIP ZEP is continuously supporting the European Commission's work on CDR through its participation in the expert group on carbon removals. These items are further detailed below.

3.1 Workshop with the European Commission

On 9 December 2022, ETIP ZEP organised a virtual workshop with Mr Fabien Ramos, from the EC's Directorate-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA). The session started with a presentation of the then recently adopted European Commission proposal on a Union certification framework for carbon removals.

Following the presentation, there was an opportunity for participants to discuss and ask questions. The discussion was centred around the implementation timeline of the policy file, the application of the proposed certification schemes on the different value chain operators, the additionality requirements, and the scope of the expert group on carbon removals.

⁷ [CDR Mission released its Innovation Roadmap \(2022\)](#)

⁸ [CDR Mission Innovation Launchpad \(2022\)](#)

3.2 Feedback to the European Commission proposal on the certification framework for carbon removals

ETIP ZEP / TWG CDR submitted feedback⁹ to the co-legislators through the call for feedback on the adopted proposal for a regulation establishing a Union certification framework for carbon removals. The group's response focused on the importance of establishing an accurate definition of what constitutes carbon removals, the recognition of permanent solutions, supported by thorough carbon accounting from a life-cycle perspective, as well as on the interaction with other international frameworks.

3.3 Input to the Article 6.4 Supervisory Body call for input on carbon removals

In preparing a response to the Article 6.4 Supervisory Bod call for views on carbon removals¹⁰, the TWG CDR developed six integrity principles that an effective CDR sector aligned with climate and sustainability objectives must adhere to:

1) Clear definition of CDR

CDR activities involve taking CO₂ out of the atmosphere, where it contributes to climate change, and storing it where it will not affect the climate for an extended period of time. It is important to avoid misconceptions and confusion with carbon reductions by accurately defining 'what is a carbon dioxide removal'. A robust and thorough definition must reflect the following principles:

1. CO₂ is physically removed from the atmosphere.
2. The removed CO₂ is stored out of the atmosphere in a manner intended to be permanent.
3. Upstream and downstream greenhouse gas emissions, associated with the removal and storage process, are comprehensively estimated and included in the emission balance.
4. The total quantity of atmospheric CO₂ removed and permanently stored is greater than the total quantity of CO₂ emitted to the atmosphere.

2) Permanence

While different activities can achieve carbon dioxide removal, they will involve different storage timeframes and risks of storage reversal. For example, storage in products and carbon farming activities will typically store CO₂ out of the atmosphere for decades to centuries; while storage of CO₂ in geological reservoirs offers the opportunity to safely store CO₂ for thousands of years.

The different timescales and reversal risks associated with the different activities should be reported, ensuring that the market is able to differentiate them (and price them accordingly), recognising the value of geological storage.

⁹ ETIP ZEP's submitted response can be found here: <https://zeroemissionsplatform.eu/response-to-the-call-for-feedback-on-the-eu-certification-framework-for-carbon-removals/>

¹⁰ [ETIP ZEP response to the Article 6.4 Supervisory Body call for views on carbon removals \(2023\)](#)

3) Accurate quantification

The quantification of carbon removals must be robust, transparent, and complete. In this sense, a cautious and comprehensive verification of principle 3 (*above*) is critical to make sure that all associated emissions are included in the life-cycle analysis (including energy/electricity input).

Crucially, this also implies that while some technologies have the potential to lead to carbon removals, a case-by-case approach is needed to ensure that projects deliver real carbon removals.

4) Robust Monitoring, Reporting and Verification

The Article 6.4 mechanism must set out robust monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) requirements related to the operation of storage sites and methods. It is essential that appropriate monitoring approaches can be introduced for all activities on an equivalent basis (i.e., conferring the same level of confidence) to regularly confirm that carbon dioxide continues to be stored out of the atmosphere. In addition, the rules and methodologies under the mechanism must lay out the responsibilities and liabilities for compensating and remedying reversals of storage.

5) Alignment with sustainability principles

The climate benefit of carbon removal activities must be viewed together with wider sustainability objectives – from biomass use and biodiversity protection to land use and energy input requirements.

It is essential that projects are designed and implemented in a manner that does not compromise environmental and sustainability safeguards.

6) International collaboration and consistency

Net-zero and net-negative objectives require large volumes of removals and a rapid scale-up, with engineered carbon removals offering the highest durability. As support frameworks for carbon removals develop, it is important to ensure consistency so that all carbon removal activities are underpinned by the same quality standards irrespectively of where they take place. This will help to establish a global level-playing field and unlock further opportunities for developers. In this sense, we encourage the Supervisory Body to collaborate with national and regional initiatives, notably the recently proposed European Union's certification scheme for carbon removal activities.

4 COORDINATION ON ACCOUNTING METHODOLOGIES

To establish an effective CDR sector, aligned with climate and environmental principles, it is important to coordinate on a global scale, namely by harmonising principles to guide the development of the sector as well as accounting methodologies.

ETIP ZEP has, for this reason, been actively participating in the Advisory Group of the CCS+ initiative¹¹, which is developing carbon accounting methodologies for Voluntary Carbon Markets, including for CDR, such as BECCS and DACS. The initiative's process is based on a modular approach, with:

- Overarching modules / tools – CCS+ methodology; Guidance and Principles document; tools for the differentiation between emission reductions and removals, baseline quantification and allocation of project emissions.
- Capture modules – capture technologies from air (DAC), post-combustion, industrial processes, oil and gas production, biogenic sources, pre-combustion and oxy-fuel combustion.
- Transport modules – pipelines, ships/barges, road/trucks and rail.
- Storage and use modules – including storage in aquifers, depleted oil and gas fields and mineralisation.
- Compliance Guidance – including recommendations on how to use the methodologies in the context of Article 6 transactions and EU compliance (e.g., EU ETS).

In addition, the CCS+ initiative will be developing a dedicated methodology framework for CDR, where ETIP ZEP will be involved. The dedicated working group will first meet on 16 May 2023, to agree on the scope of work, governance, budget and workplan.

¹¹ [CCS+ initiative](#)